

Luminous flux (radiant power, radiant flux) and solid angle through the inclined ellipse

Harald Schröer

2015

We want to determine the luminous flux (radiant power, radiant flux) and the solid angle Ω through the inclined ellipse. The method is similar to Schröer [3] (chapter 7 and 9). We view the following ellipse:

a and b are the semi-axes. r is the distance. We introduce the medium's absorption coefficient m and the luminous intensity (radiant intensity) I of the point light source Q . The angle of inclination of the ellipse is:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2}}{r}$$

M is the geometrical midpoint of the ellipse.

We use the canonical equation:

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{y}{b} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}$$

$$h(x) := y = \frac{b}{a} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}$$

We define $x_1 \in [-a, a]$ and $x_2 \in [-h(x_1), h(x_1)]$. We construct the distance vector:

$$\vec{l} = (r, x_1 + r_2, r_1 + x_2)$$

It follows:

$$l(x_1, x_2) = \sqrt{r^2 + (x_1 + r_2)^2 + (r_1 + x_2)^2}$$

Now we turn to the illumination (irradiance):

$$E(x_1, x_2) = \frac{I \cdot e^{-m \cdot l(x_1, x_2)}}{(l(x_1, x_2))^2}$$

We need the angle of inclination at (x_1, x_2) :

$$\cos \beta(x_1, x_2) = \frac{r}{l(x_1, x_2)}$$

We define:

$$f(x_1, x_2) := E(x_1, x_2) \cdot \cos \beta(x_1, x_2)$$

We construct the luminous flux (radiant power, radiant flux) through the ellipse:

$$\Phi = \int_{-a-h(x)}^a \int_{-h(x)}^{h(x)} f(x_1, x_2) dx_2 dx_1 \quad (1)$$

We see the approximation for $a, b \ll r$:

$$\Phi \approx \frac{I \cdot e^{-m \cdot \sqrt{r^2 + r_1^2 + r_2^2}} \cdot \pi ab \cdot \cos \alpha}{r^2 + r_1^2 + r_2^2} \quad (2)$$

with:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2}}{r}$$

With $m = 0$ and without I we get the solid angle through the ellipse.

We find a program to calculate (1) at Robinson [2].

We reduce the solid angle to an one-dimensional integral:

Let be $m = 0$ and we calculate the interior integral of (1):

$$\int_{-h(x_1)}^{h(x_1)} \frac{dx_2}{(l(x_1, x_2))^3} = \left[\frac{2 \cdot (2x_2 + 2r_1)}{\Delta \cdot l(x_1, x_2)} \right]_{x_2=-h(x_1)}^{x_2=h(x_1)} =: Z(x_1)$$

with

$$l(x_1, x_2)^2 = x_2^2 + 2r_1x_2 + r_1^2 + (x_1 + r_2)^2 + r^2$$

and

$$\Delta := 4 \cdot (r_1^2 + (x_1 + r_2)^2 + r^2) - 4r_1^2$$

For the integration see Bronstein [1] number 242 p.49.

The solid angle can be written as:

$$\Omega = r \cdot \int_{-a}^a Z(x_1) dx_1 \quad (3)$$

We can use numerical methods for example the Simpson's rule. Now two examples will be treated:

We calculate the solid angle through an inclined ellipse for $a=7\text{m}, b=3\text{m}, r_1=50\text{m}$ and $r_2=25\text{m}$. In the third column are the results of the approximation. The calculations with the Simpson's rule (40 steps) are in the fourth column. We have the following table:

r [m]	angle of inclination [degree]	solid angle [steradian]	solid angle [steradian]
100	29.2059	0.00438753	0.00437565
90	31.8457	0.00499266	0.00497880
80	34.9447	0.00567756	0.00566158
70	38.6107	0.00642391	0.00640597
60	42.9749	0.00717765	0.00715854
50	48.1897	0.00781908	0.00780068
40	54.4147	0.00812506	0.00811059
30	61.7795	0.00775071	0.00774372
20	70.3143	0.00630464	0.00630586
10	79.8579	0.00360226	0.00360650
9	80.8540	0.00327089	0.00327498
8	81.8558	0.00293074	0.00293460
7	82.8626	0.00258260	0.00258616
6	83.8738	0.00222733	0.00223051
5	84.8889	0.00186584	0.00186859
4	85.9072	0.00149909	0.00150136
3	86.9281	0.00112809	0.00112983
2	87.9510	0.00075386	0.00075504
1	88.9752	0.00037747	0.00037807
0.5	89.4875	0.00018880	0.00018910
0.4	89.5900	0.00015105	0.00015129
0.3	89.6925	0.00011329	0.00011347
0.2	89.7950	0.000075529	0.000075649
0.1	89.8975	0.000037765	0.000037825
0.05	89.9488	0.000018883	0.000018913
0.04	89.9590	0.000015106	0.000015130
0.03	89.9693	0.000011330	0.000011348
0.02	89.9795	0.0000075531	0.0000075650
0.01	89.9898	0.0000037765	0.0000037825

The results of the third and fourth column agree approximately.

Now we view a further example with $r_1 = r_2 = 0$. Thus the angle of inclination is zero degree. We choose $a=7m$ and $b=3m$. Then we obtain the following table. The result of the approximation are in the second column and the results of Simpson's rule are in the third column:

r [m]	solid angle(steradian)	solid angle(steradian)
100	0.00659734	0.00657231
90	0.00814487	0.00810986
80	0.0103084	0.0102568
70	0.0134640	0.0133828
60	0.0183260	0.0181867
50	0.0263894	0.0261205
40	0.0412334	0.0406186
30	0.0733038	0.0714783
20	0.164934	0.156356
10	0.659734	0.547625
9	0.814487	0.651973
8	1.030835	0.786842
7	1.346397	0.964295
6	1.832596	1.202322
5	2.638938	1.528115
4	4.123340	1.982897
3	7.330383	2.627329
2	16.49336	3.539954
1	65.97345	4.780222
0.5	263.894	5.46640
0.4	412.334	5.55807
0.3	733.038	5.59070
0.2	1649.34	5.61333
0.1	6597.34	6.08208
0.05	26389.4	6.15986
0.04	41233.4	6.21775
0.03	73303.8	6.23641
0.02	164933.6	6.25205
0.01	659734.5	6.26762

If r is small the approximation is inaccurate. We remark that the last 6 results of Simpson's rule are calculated with 200,400,800,1600,3200 and 6400 steps. The other results of Simpson's rule are obtained with 40 steps. The accurate results are always smaller than $2 \cdot \pi$.

References

- [1] Bronstein, Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik", 22.edition Teubner Verlag Leipsic 1985

- [2] Robinson, de Doncker, "Algorithm 45, Automatic computation of improper integrals over a bounded or unbounded planar region", Computing, 27 (1981) 3, p.253-284
- [3] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination", german and english edition, Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001